

*a non-profit
research institute affiliated
with the University of
Bergen*

*Jahnebakken 3,
N-5007 Bergen
Norway*

NERSC Technical Report no. 419

**USING QGIS FOR ORGANISING, VISUALISING
AND PUBLISHING IN SITU OBSERVATIONS, DRONE
MOSAICS AND SATELLITE IMAGERY OF ARCTIC
SEA ICE**

by
Tor I. Olausen
Torill Hamre
Frode Monsen

	<p>Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) Jahnebakken 3, N-5007 Bergen, Norway Phone: + 47 55 20 58 00 Fax: + 47 55 20 58 01 E-mail: post@nersc.no http://www.nersc.no</p>
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TITLE:	REPORT IDENTIFICATION: NERSC Technical Report 419
CLIENT: Research Council of Norway	CONTRACT: Digital Arctic Shipping - New data products and visualisation services (project number 309708)
CLIENT REFERENCE:	AVAILABILITY: Public
INVESTIGATORS: Tor I. Olaussen Torill Hamre Frode Monsen	AUTHORISATION:
	DATE: 4 October 2022

SUMMARY: This report documents how QGIS was installed and used at NERSC in the Digital Arctic Shipping project to organise, visualise and publish sea ice data from several sources. QGIS is an open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) that is available on all major computer platforms, and maintained by a large community world-wide contributing to the Open Source Geospatial Foundation (OSGeo). We have used QGIS Desktop, a GIS running on a local computer, to organise sea ice data in different formats, spatial resolutions, and map projections into a coherent structure. This structure is called a QGIS project, which in addition to listing the individual data layers defines how data can be published through a standard interface in a given map projection and format. By organising related sea ice data in a QGIS project, we can publish them using the QGIS Server application. This allows users to visualise and access the data through their web browser without having to install any local software or plugins. Together, QGIS Desktop and QGIS Server provide a flexible solution for sharing sea ice data between scientists and with users in public and private sector. The examples of different sea ice data shown in this report illustrates some of the capabilities offered by a QGIS based solution. Our proof-of-concept QGIS system can be developed further to support scientific data analysis and provide services for vessels operating in sea ice infested areas in the Arctic.

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1. Introduction

QGIS is an open source Geographic Information System available for use on all major computer platforms (Windows, MacOS, Linux). QGIS is available both as a regular desktop application and as a server. QGIS is under active development and has numerous plugins/add-ons to support a plethora of file formats and external services. QGIS supports the import and use of both raster and vector data. The QGIS Documentation site provides a nice introduction to GIS in general and to the rich functionality of QGIS [0].

This report focuses on the use of QGIS in relation to Digital Arctic Shipping where we combine ship tracks, drone mosaics, in situ ice measurements and photographs into QGIS projects and present the data via the web.

2. QGIS Desktop

QGIS Desktop is used to configure, import and register the various raster and vector data into projects and layers within projects. The configuration includes geographic projection, background layers, such as land and bathymetry outlines, publishing options (i.e. WMS).

QGIS Desktop is the main tool for importing, configuring and working with data. One begins by creating a new project, where each piece of data is put into separate layers.

Often one goal of the work done in QGIS Desktop will be to publish the project to QGIS Server, therefore a good practice is to first gather all local data files into one folder before importing. This will make it easy to share the project, since everything related can be found in a single location.

2.1. QGIS Desktop Installation

The installation of QGIS Desktop is well covered elsewhere. We provide links for the supported operating systems. The main page for QGIS Installers is: <https://www.qgis.org/en/site/forusers/alldownloads.html>. This page provides links to detailed installation instructions.

2.1.1. Windows installation

<https://www.qgis.org/en/site/forusers/alldownloads.html#windows>

2.1.2. MacOS installation

<https://www.qgis.org/en/site/forusers/alldownloads.html#mac-os-x-macos>

2.1.3. Linux installation

<https://www.qgis.org/en/site/forusers/alldownloads.html#mac-os-x-macos>

2.2. New Project Settings

2.2.1. Creating a QGIS project

After launching QGIS Desktop, select “New” from the “Project” menu. A blank, empty view will be shown (Fig,1).

Figure 1. Creating a new project in QGIS Desktop.

To ensure that the project file is kept together with the data, save the project now to a new, empty folder. The following image shows the save project dialog, where a new folder “New_project”, and the project “new_project.qgs” is entered (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Storing the QGIS project in a format that allows for publishing using QGIS Server.

Two things to note in the above:

1. The folder name and project file name are entered without spaces or other special characters
2. The project file name includes “.qgs” as the file suffix. This will save the project in a more compatible file format for publishing to QGIS Server. The default file format for newer versions of QGIS is “.qgz”, which is a compressed form. In the cases where an existing project with the suffix “.qgz” is used, a “.qgs” file can be saved by opening the “.qgz” file in QGIS Desktop, and selecting “Save As...” from the “Project”. Change the “.qgz” suffix the “.qgs” and save the file.

2.2.2. Setting properties to prepare for publication

To set various properties for the new project, select “Properties...” from the “Project” menu (Fig.3). Here, it is important to use relative paths to data files to ensure the data are found when published using QGIS Server.

Figure 3. Setting project properties to enable publishing using QGIS Server.

As one of the goals is to publish to QGIS Server, an important area in the Properties dialog is the “QGIS Server” tab, as shown below (Fig.4).

Figure 4. Setting service capabilities properties for publishing data via QGIS Server.

Also, setting WMS properties is needed to allow for data layers to be positioned correctly on the map (Fig.5).

Figure 5. Setting Web Map Service properties for publishing data via QGIS Server.

2.3. Data import

QGIS supports many types of data and file types. In this context we will import raster data as GeoTIFF, and vector data as both CSV and Shapefiles.

2.3.1. Import of raster data (Drone mosaics)

Once a QGIS project has been created, we are ready to populate it with data layers. The first step is usually to add a background map, such as shown in the map area below (Fig.6). Then, the next step is adding one or more data layers. To import raster data, select the “Layer” -> “Add Layer” -> “Add Raster Layer” menu (Fig.6). Add the image by clicking on the “...” symbol in the “Source” section of the dialog and navigating to the image. Select the file, click “Add” and close the dialog by clicking “Close” (Fig.7). The image that was just imported, will show up as a layer in the “Layers” panel (Fig.8).

Figure 6. Navigating QGIS menus to add a raster data layer to a project.

Figure 7. Selecting a data file for a new layer and adding it to the project.

Figure 8. Displaying the new layer in the map area of QGIS.

As mentioned previously, it is beneficial to copy all your data files to a single folder before importing them. This makes it easier to transfer the project, and is necessary for the QGIS server to locate the data that corresponds to the project's layers.

2.3.2. Import of vector data (Ship tracks)

Two methods of importing vector data will be shown:

1. Formatted, well-known vector data such as ARCGIS Shape (.shp) files can be imported directly by selecting “Layer” -> “Add Layer” -> “Add Vector Layer” menu (Fig.9). Then select a known data file format such as an ESRI shapefile (.shp). This is done by clicking on the “...” symbol in the “Source” section of the dialog and navigating to the file (Fig.10).

Figure 9. Navigating QGIS menus to add a vector data layer to a project.

Figure 10. Selecting a data file containing vector data for the new layer.

2. CSV data must be imported by selecting “Layer” -> “Add Layer” -> “Add delimited Text Layer” menu (Fig.11). Then select the CSV file. It is possible to preview the file and assign the correct columns to longitude and latitude (Fig.12). Click the “Add” button and then the “Close” button. The file will appear on the map and in the layers panel to the left (Fig.13).

Figure 11. Navigating QGIS menus to add a data layer from a delimited text file to a project.

Figure 12. Inspecting the imported CSV file to verify that the geometry definition is read correctly.

Figure 13. The imported CSV file has been added to the project and visualised on the map.

When the aim is to export the project to QGIS Server, it is important to configure *each* layer appropriately. By right-clicking on a layer and selecting “Properties”, select the QGIS Server tab and fill in at least the “Short name” and “Title” fields (Fig.14)

Figure 14. Defining layer properties for publishing via QGIS Server.

2.3.3. Web scraping and data import

The ICEWATCH website (<https://icewatch.met.no/>) is used as an example of obtaining external data and adding it to QGIS. ICEWATCH provides a near continuous record of ice observations and photos for selected cruises in sea ice infested areas (Fig.15). The ice observations can be downloaded as a CSV file, however the photos are only available online at the site (Fig.16).

Figure 15. Screenshot of icewatch.met.no website..

Figure 16. Screenshot of icewatch.met.no photo gallery for a single observation.

A Python script has been created to scrape the URLs of the photos on the ICEWATCH website, and append the URLs to the CSV file. For each observation row, the URLs to each photograph is appended as an additional column. This CSV file is imported to the project as described above, then the URL columns are changed to IMAGE format, so that when displayed the images will be downloaded dynamically without having to download all images beforehand and storing them locally (Fig.17).

Figure 17. Example of QGIS displaying linked photos from icewatch.met.no for a single ice station.

3. QGIS Server/Services

We have chosen to use the following distribution of QGIS Server with corresponding services, distributed as Docker containers (Fig. 18):

<https://github.com/qwc-services/qwc-docker> [1]

Figure 18. Github.com page for QGIS Services as docker images.

3.1. QGIS Server installation

This distribution provides a complete installation, and can be run on a server and locally for testing purposes.

A working Docker and docker-compose installation is required on the server or the local testing machine. See the Docker homepage (<https://www.docker.com/>) for installation instructions on your preferred platform. In addition, a Git client is needed.

Clone the repository:

```
git clone https://github.com/qwc-services/qwc-docker.git
```

and follow the instructions given on the GitHub page.

3.2. Docker images

As mentioned, there is a complete set of services delivered as separate Docker images, the most used are; QGIS Server, Admin GUI and interactive map viewer.

3.3. Starting and Stopping QGIS Server²²

To start all the docker images:

```
docker-compose up -d
```

To stop all the docker images:

```
docker-compose down
```

3.4. Adding Projects

When all the layers in the project have been configured for QGIS server, and all the files that the project consists of are in one directory, this directory must be uploaded to the server.

There is an import directory that the configuration generator checks, the default location is:

```
qwc-docker/volumes/qgs-resources/scan/
```

Upload the whole project directory there.

In the following, we use a generic domain (qgis.example.com). Substitute this generic domain with your actual domain, or if the system is installed locally, use <http://localhost:8088>. The default username/password are admin/admin. The first time you log in, you will be asked to change the password. Login to the admin GUI here (Fig.19):

http://qgis.example.com/qwc_admin

Figure 19. Login page for QGIS Admin GUI.

Click on the “Resources” menu, then click on the button “Import maps” (Fig.20).

All the maps will be listed in the “scan” directory, click on the “New Permission” to the right of the map that was just uploaded.

Figure 20. QGIS Admin GUI for importing maps and setting permissions.

Select “public” from the “Role” menu, and click on the “write” checkbox to enable writing (Fig.21). From the qwc-services documentation [1]: “The write flag is only used for data resources and sets whether a data layer is read-only”. Then click the “Save” button.

Figure 21. Permissions options for QGIS project in the Admin GUI.

Click on the “Home” menu and then click the button “Generate service configuration” (Fig.22).

Figure 22. Configuration generation page after adding a new QGIS project.

If the new project was configured correctly, it will be included in the newly generated configuration.

Navigate to:

<http://qgis.example.com:8088>

This is the interactive map viewer. Each project is called a “Theme” and can be selected from the “Themes” menu in the “Map & Tools” menu.

Figure 23. Theme selection menu from the interactive map viewer.

The selected theme will be displayed and can be interacted with in several ways.

OBJ-OBJ

3.5. Zoom levels and navigation

When the project has successfully been imported and selected in the “Themes” menu, it is displayed in the interactive map viewer. All layers in the project are available in the “Layers” menu (Fig.24).

Figure 24. Layer selection menu from the interactive map viewer.

Layers can be turned off and on, new layers can be added, either from online sources (WMS, etc) or by uploading a file as seen in Fig.25.

Figure 25. Import layer option in the Layer menu.

There are several other options in the “Map & Tools” menu, among them a “Login” option. It is possible to integrate this system with a local LDAP/Active Directory authentication system, and thereby restrict projects to specific users or groups.

From the toolbar on top of the window, it is possible to select various measurement tools, such as distance and area, and print a portion of the map with grid lines, etc. (Fig.26)

Figure 26. The Map & Tools menu from the interactive map viewer.

4. QGIS Web client

For those who have an existing QGIS server installation, there is a QGIS Web Client that can be used from your local computer to connect, view and interact with published maps:

<https://github.com/qgis/qwc2-demo-app> [2]

5. QGIS Integrations

QGIS is fully compatible with Python. It is possible to create custom plugins or scripts that integrate with external services or automate repetitive tasks:

https://www.qgistutorials.com/en/docs/3/building_a_python_plugin.html [4]

https://www.qgistutorials.com/en/docs/running_qgis_jobs.html [5]

5.1. QGIS Plugin for ARCMAP [3]

A QGIS plugin for ARCMAP has been created, where it is possible to connect to the ARCMAP API and insert layers of data from there.

6. Automation of operations

6.1. Python scripts

QGIS has a `qgis.core` module available to python users. This module is needed to interact with QGIS, in addition to knowing the paths to the local QGIS installation and required libraries (i.e. GDAL, etc).

The actual process is documented in detail in the links above, but the main procedure is:

1. Create a batch/shell script file.
2. Set the necessary path variables to identify required libraries and binaries in the batch/shell script file.
3. Create a python file to do processing.
4. Call the python file from the batch/shell script file.
5. Run the batch/shell script to start the processing.

6.2. Task Scheduler/Cron jobs

Once the batch/shell script and python processing files are created and tested, it is easy to set them up to run on a schedule by configuring the Task Scheduler on Windows or a cron job on MacOS/Linux.

7. References

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